

MULTISCALE MODELLING APPROACH FOR FLEXIBLE RISERS

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ABSTRACT

Due to structural complexities in unbonded flexible riser pipes, predicting stresses and instability failures in these components remains challenging. In this article, we present developments in the linking of small scale local nonlinear structural behavior with large scale global dynamic analysis. Multiscale formulations aimed at improving modeling accuracy in a computationally feasible form are presented. A nested multiscale procedure is developed in which global model and Representative Volume Element (RVE) model of flexible pipes are run in parallel. The global model consists of hybrid beam elements adopting an elastic-plastic constitutive model and multiscale elements whose constitutive response are determined from the RVE analysis. The global model passes field variables such as displacements and rotations to the RVE model and the RVE model returns the tangent stiffness of the multiscale elements for the large scale analysis in a nested manner. This procedure can serve as the framework for assessing fatigue damage, predicting instability failure modes and investigating the consequences of damage, such as breaking of the tensile armor wires in flexible risers.

1 INTRODUCTION

Unbonded flexible risers are composite pipe structures to transfer fluids between the seabed and surface platforms for subsea oil and gas production. They consist of multiple steel wires, polymer layers and interlocking metallic layers which are able to move relative to each other. Flexible risers exhibit non-linear structural behavior under axial loading, bending and torsional loading due to the geometric nonlinearity of helical configurations, material nonlinearity of polymeric layers and boundary nonlinearity due to internal contact and friction interactions. Of particular interest is the displacement and stick-slip mechanism governing the behavior of the tensile armor wires as this leads to the low bending stiffness of flexible pipes. When the pipe curvature is small, the structure has a high bending stiffness and no slip of the tensile armor wires relative to underlying layers occurs. As the curvature is increased, differential shear forces overcome friction and the tendons begin to slide, leading to a reduction in the bending stiffness.

This article proposes a sequential multiscale modelling methodology for flexible pipes. We employ a global model using nonlinear co-rotational hybrid beam elements with the constitutive model for these elements derived from a detailed local finite element (FE) model. A new nonlinear constitutive model is described that relates stress in pipe components to force and moment resultants at flexible pipe

sections. A detailed three dimensional finite element model of a flexible pipe is introduced as a means of determining the pipe's response with as few simplifying assumptions as possible and providing data for calibration of the constitutive and empirical models. Finally, a suitable beam element for use in global analysis of a flexible riser or riser system is described.

2 MULTI SCALE MODELING OF FLEXIBLE PIPES

To investigate non-linear behavior of solid structures, multi-scale analyses based on global-local models have been studied by many researchers in literature [1–3]. Generally, a global FE analysis is performed on a global region with coarse finite elements, followed by a detailed local FE analysis performed in a local region with an independent three-dimensional fine mesh. The main limitation of this approach is that the occurrence of certain local nonlinear phenomena (such as strain localization, contact/separation, concrete damage, fibre pull-out or delamination of composite materials) may influence the response of the structure on the global scale and this cannot be captured with this procedure. To overcome this, multi-scale modelling techniques based on the homogenization of a Representative Volume Element (RVE) of the material have been used [3–5].

A widely used-framework for simulating materials and structures where a large difference in size exists between characteristic length scales of global and local structures and phenomena is that of computational homogenization. Using this method, a detailed model that is representative of the small-scale structure is created. Global simulations are carried out on a large-scale model that is assumed to be homogeneous. For selected material points in the large-scale model, strains are passed to the small scale model. Simulations are then carried out on the small-scale model to determine the stress-response to the large-scale model. In this way, the small-scale representative model acts as the constitutive model for the large-scale model. Transferal of stresses and strains between model is usually effected by volumetric averaging of stresses and imposition of specialized boundary conditions on the small-scale model, as specified by the so-called Hill-Mandel condition of energy equivalence between scales. Although computational homogenization is typically used to relate large- and small-scale finite element models comprising of continuum finite elements, some authors have extended this approach for use with structural elements (see e.g. Coenen [6]). Linking methods to incorporate nonlinear small-scale response into large-scale analysis of risers by constitutive models have been developed by Tan et al [7]. A nonlinear dynamic sub structuring approach for scale linking in flexible pipes has been developed by Majed et al [8]. This method is developed as an extension of substructuring techniques used for dynamic analysis of large linear structures.

NESTED MULTISCALE FRAMEWORK

Due to the structural complexity of unbonded flexible risers, detailed FE modeling of full-length flexible pipes including individual riser layers is challenging and computationally expensive. Instead, we employ user-defined hybrid beam elements for the global analysis of flexible pipe with the effective properties derived from RVE analysis of the pipe in advance. Additionally, to improve the prediction of stresses and deformations in the local regions of flexible pipe where failure and structural instabilities are expected, a 'nested' multiscale framework is proposed in which the RVE analysis of critical regions or the regions of interest is performed concurrently with the global analysis. User-defined multiscale elements are employed at these interest regions in the global model to allow for a multiscale linking procedure to be implemented. Associated RVE models of these elements are detailed representative of a pipe segment considering behavior of individual layers and their interactions corresponding to the applied load levels obtained from the global scale. At every load increment, the macro loads of the multiscale elements are computed and passed to the associated RVE

models. Upon solving the RVE boundary problems, the RVE stiffness is updated back to the multiscale elements for the next global step. A consistent linking between the global and local models enables a more interactive multiscale method in which the stiffness and stress of the critical elements keep updated through every load step.

The proposed multiscale framework is able to overcome many disadvantages of traditional global-local methods and the multiscale approaches based on homogenization theories. Most global-local multiscale approaches involve solving a local region from a macro load prescription, but the resultant local material behavior does not affect the global response in return. On the other hand, multiscale homogenization theories allow for more interaction between different model scales but it requires the multiscale analyses to be performed at every material point in the global model which is not necessary in some cases. Our proposed nested multiscale framework has advantages in that the local analyses need only be done at specified regions in parallel with the global analysis, thus saving computational effort.

In the afore-mentioned multiscale approach, the global analysis is divided into a series of load steps where local stiffness of the multiscale elements are updated to provide more accurate prediction of the global response. The global model consists of simple elements such as hybrid beam elements and multiscale elements at critical regions. The global elements can adopt a nonlinear constitutive model based on pre-defined effective properties of the pipe whereas multiscale elements follow a user-defined constitutive law with constitutive properties/stiffness unspecified at the beginning of the analysis. The stiffness of multiscale elements is obtained and updated from a separate RVE analyses. The constitutive models of hybrid beam elements and the multiscale elements are coded into a user-defined element subroutine (UEL) in ABAQUS. The proposed multiscale scheme and its linking method are implemented using a Python script. The flowchart of the nested multiscale is described in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Flowchart of the nested multiscale framework

Application of the multiscale method

The application of the proposed multiscale method for a global-local analysis of a flexible pipe is demonstrated here. The global pipe model comprises a majority of standard beam elements (B33) in Abaqus and one multiscale element defined as a user defined element. The standard beam B33 elements employ an elastic-plastic material model while the multiscale element is assigned with a linear generalized stress-strain behaviour implemented in a user-defined UEL subroutine. The constitutive properties of the multiscale element are unknown at the start of the analysis and only derived from the local analyses of its associated RVE model. Details of the model are shown in Fig. 2. Load is applied at one end of the pipe while the other pipe end is fixed. The prediction of the multiscale model is compared to a global model with full beam elements of B33 type without multiscale element. The predicted results by the standalone beam model (without multiscale element) and the multiscale model show good correlations. The advantage of the multiscale model over the stand alone beam model lies in its capability to provide detailed responses of local structures in an efficient manner without fully modeling the whole pipe structure.

Figure 2: Description of the nested multiscale model with many standard beam elements and one UEL multiscale element with its associated RVE

ELEMENT DEVELOPMENT FOR GLOBAL ANALYSIS

To provide a large-scale model for use in the multiscale analysis, a suitable global analysis model is required. A finite element model using structural finite elements was chosen to represent riser length in order that nonlinear, coupled response models could be implemented. The finite element software package Abaqus was used to carry out global analyses and a user-defined element was coded to represent riser elements. In order to avoid numerical problems associated with the low flexural stiffness of flexible pipes a hybrid beam element based on the work of McNamara et al [9] was used. In addition, a corotational formulation was used to enable the element to undergo large displacements

and rotations. It was shown that the resulting element gave much better performance for flexible riser applications than standard Abaqus beam elements.

A 3D co-rotational hybrid beam element (HBE), using Kirchhoff assumption, is developed for static and dynamic analyses of flexible riser. The geometric constraint $\bar{\varepsilon} = \bar{N} / EA$ of the beam is imposed by Lagrange multiplier. The Lagrange multiplier is identified as the axial force, hence, one can achieve the augmented internal virtual work as follows

$$\delta W^{int} = \int \bar{N} \delta \bar{\varepsilon} + \bar{\mathbf{M}} \delta \bar{\boldsymbol{\chi}} + (\bar{\varepsilon} - \bar{N} / EA) \delta \bar{N}, \quad (1)$$

where \bar{N} is the axial force, $\bar{\mathbf{M}}$ is the bending moment vector, $\bar{\boldsymbol{\chi}}$ is the curvature vector, $\bar{\varepsilon}$ is the axial strain, E is Young's modulus, and A is the area of the beam section.

Figure 1 Beam kinematics and co-rotational coordinates

Assume, at the n -th time step the global DOFs in one HBE element are defined as ${}^n \mathbf{d}^g = ({}^n \mathbf{u}_1^{gT}, {}^n \boldsymbol{\theta}_1^{gT}, {}^n \mathbf{u}_2^{gT}, {}^n \boldsymbol{\theta}_2^{gT}, {}^n \bar{N})^T$. ${}^n \mathbf{u}_i^g$ and ${}^n \boldsymbol{\theta}_i^g$ denote the global translational and rotational DOFs at two end nodes, respectively. The finite rotation is described by additive rotational vector in this research, which is based on the parameterization of the finite 3D rotations [10]. The local DOFs of HBE element are defined by ${}^n \mathbf{d}^l = ({}^n \bar{u}, {}^n \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_1^T, {}^n \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_2^T, {}^n \bar{N})^T$. ${}^n \bar{u}$ is the axial displacement. ${}^n \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_i$ are defined as the local nodal rotations. In Figure 1, the local frame in the initial configuration can be defined by $\mathbf{R}_o = [e_1^o \ e_2^o \ e_3^o]$, where e_i^o are the basis vectors of the global Cartesian coordinates. The element triad can be defined by ${}^n \mathbf{R}_r = [{}^n r_1 \ {}^n r_2 \ {}^n r_3]$. The nodal triads can be updated by ${}^n \mathbf{R}_i^g = \exp({}^n \boldsymbol{\theta}_i^g)$. The generalized strain vector $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^l$ and stress vector in the local coordinates can be defined as

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^l = (\bar{u} / l_0 \ \bar{\chi}_1 \ \bar{\chi}_2 \ \bar{\chi}_3 \ \bar{N})^T = \mathbf{B}^l \mathbf{d}^l. \quad (2)$$

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^l = (\bar{N} \ \bar{m}_1 \ \bar{m}_2 \ \bar{m}_3 \ \bar{u} / l_0 - \bar{N} / EA)^T \quad (3)$$

where, \mathbf{B}^l is the displacement-strain matrix, $\bar{\chi}_i$ is the local curvature component and \bar{m}_i is the bending moment component. The local internal force vector and tangent stiffness matrix can be written as follows

$${}^n \mathbf{f}^l = \int_l (\mathbf{B}^l)^T \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^l, \quad \mathbf{K}^l = \int_l (\mathbf{B}^l)^T \mathbf{D}^l \mathbf{B}^l. \quad (4)$$

where the generalized stress $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^l$ and material response tensor \mathbf{D}^l are computed by using the proposed constitutive model in this research. Using the coordinate transformation matrix, one can achieve the global internal force vector and tangent stiffness matrix as below,

$$\mathbf{f}^g = \mathbf{B}_{trans}^T \mathbf{f}^l, \quad \mathbf{K}^g = \mathbf{B}_{trans}^T \mathbf{K}^l \mathbf{B}_{trans} + \mathbf{K}_G. \quad (5)$$

Here B_{trans} is the coordinate transformation matrix and K_G is the geometric nonlinear stiffness matrix. The above formulations have been coded as an Abaqus UEL user subroutine in order to carry out implicit static or dynamic analyses. In the dynamic analysis, Hilber-Hughes-Taylor time integration algorithm [11] is employed which is supported by Abaqus UEL.

Numerical Example

This example shows the results of dynamic analysis of a flexible riser system under in-plane wave loading. The riser is assumed to be straight in the initial state (see Figure 7). The riser configuration is specified by defining the ends of the riser, in fully-stretched and in the final installed condition. The global coordinates of the end on the seabed (soil anchor) is $(0,0,0)$, denoted by the end A, and the initial global coordinates of the hang-off point is $(250,0,0)$, denoted by the end B. Buoyancy modules are set at the riser span from $(75,0,0)$ to $(150,0,0)$. 80 equal-size elements are used to discretize the flexible riser. The Rayleigh damping coefficients $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\beta = 0.0$ are arbitrarily chosen to create an artificial damping in order to dissipate the kinetic energy for finding the equilibrium configuration of the installed riser, and to eliminate the undesired high-frequency oscillations in the dynamic analysis of the riser under dynamic loading.

Figure 7: Schematic of the initial configuration and the configuration after installation

The installation procedure is first carried out to find the equilibrium state of the flexible riser with gravity and buoyancy modules. In the installation procedure, there is no wave loading applied. The riser span from $(0,0,0)$ to $(50,0,0)$ is attached to the seabed. After the installation, the end B is moved to the target location $(200.0, 0.0, 100.0)$. The loading conditions and boundary conditions are illustrated in Figure and given as follows:

Loading conditions

Gravity is applied on the whole riser in the global x_3 direction with $g = -9.8m/s^2$. Buoyancy force is applied on the region $75m \leq x \leq 150m$ in the initial configuration riser in the global x_3 direction with the magnitude 3000N/m. Buoyancy loads are applied using the distributed load key U1003

Boundary conditions

$u_i = 0, i = 1, 2, 3$ at end A.

$u_2 = u_3 = 0$ and all other DOFs are free, at $0 < x_1 \leq 50$ m.

$u_1 = -50m$ and $u_3 = 100m$, and all other DOFs are free, at end B.

After all loading conditions are applied and the end B is moved to the target location, we consider the equilibrium state achieved while the kinetic energy is dissipated due to the artificial damping. Figure 2 shows the final equilibrium configuration after the installation with both gravity and buoyancy.

Figure 2 Configuration after installation with gravity and buoyancy (x_1x_3 view).

The stable periodic dynamic responses are successfully solved using Abaqus/Standard implicit dynamic solver with the developed UEL and constitutive model. The UEL has the capability to solve the dynamic responses of the flexible riser under both in-plane and out-of-plane loading.

3 CONCLUSIONS

In this article, a sequential multiscale analysis has been described and implemented. A hybrid beam element has also been coded to implement the constitutive model and represent riser elements for global analysis. The combination of these elements in a full sequential multiscale analysis is demonstrated. This procedure is distinguished from a standard global-local analysis procedure by the incorporation of realistic nonlinear behavior in global analysis and the use of more accurate boundary conditions in carrying out local analyses, and implemented in general-purpose finite element software. Use of this procedure can lead to better estimates of fatigue life of tensile armour wires.

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